

Intervention of Public Policy in Ameliorating Dementia Risk Among Nigerian Women: A Sociopolitical and Structural Determinants Review

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Article information

Date Submitted: 10/01/2026

Date Accepted: 03/03/2026

Date Published: 31/03/2026

ABSTRACT

Dementia prevalence is rising globally and fastest in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Evidence indicates that low educational attainment, short adult stature which reflects early-life undernutrition, and chronic glucose dysfunction significantly elevate dementia risk among Nigerian women. These risk factors are deeply embedded within broader sociopolitical and structural determinants of health. This review examines sociological and political dimensions of dementia risk among Nigerian women, and highlight how gender inequality, educational disadvantage and structural poverty contribute to cognitive decline across the life course. Drawing on multidisciplinary evidence from epidemiology, endocrinology, developmental health science, gender studies, and the political economy of health, this article proposes an integrated conceptual framework linking health structural determinants to cognitive aging. A comprehensive reform agenda is proposed to include establishment of a national dementia action framework, strengthening gender-responsive education systems, expanding maternal and early-life nutrition programs, and improving diabetes prevention and management policies. This narrative review demonstrates that dementia in Nigerian women reflects structural inequities that require multisectoral policy responses to bridge the gap between biomedical care and social reform.

Keywords: Dementia, developmental origins of health and disease (DOHaD), early-life adversity, gender inequality, Nigerian women, public policy, social determinants of health

INTRODUCTION

Dementia is a significant public health challenge in the 21st century, with increasing global prevalence and substantial implications for health systems and economic development.^{1,2} Although it was historically considered a condition affecting high-income countries, the burden is rapidly shifting toward LMICs, where population aging and epidemiological transitions are in acceleration.^{2,3}

Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa, is experiencing demographic aging alongside a rising burden of noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) and urbanisation.^{4,5} Despite this demographic transition, the country remains inadequately prepared to address the health and social needs associated with cognitive aging and neurodegenerative diseases.⁵ Recent biomedical and epidemiological studies have identified a cluster of determinants particularly relevant to dementia risk among Nigerian women, including low educational

How to cite this article

*Efosa Kenneth Oghagbon, Enoga Ijachi Ben-Ameh, Member Euginia George-Genyi. Intervention of Public Policy in Ameliorating Dementia Risk Among Nigerian Women: A Sociopolitical and Structural Determinants Review. *J Biomed Res Clin Pract*: 2026;9(1):41-51. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20054553>

Access to the article

Website: <http://www.jbrcp.org>

doi: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20054553

attainment, short adult stature, and glucose dysfunction such as diabetes.⁶⁻⁸ These findings align with the life-course perspective, which emphasises that cumulative exposures from early life to adulthood influence long-term cognitive outcomes.^{2,9}

The essence of this work therefore was to evaluate the gender related factors that predisposes Nigeria women to higher dementia risk and to see if there are gaps in sociopolitical spheres that can be modulated to improve disease susceptibility among this group. by so doing, government and relevant agencies can be called upon to act accordingly and mitigate the burden of this disease, especially in the women

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This narrative review employs a multidisciplinary narrative synthesis of literature examining dementia risk factors relevant to Nigerian women. Peer-reviewed articles were identified from databases including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Additional sources included reports from non-peer-reviewed literature was obtained from; WHO, World Alzheimer Report, UNICEF, Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS). Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) and National Nutrition and Health Survey (NNHS) were also retrieved and analyzed. The search items used were: (“dementia” or “Alzheimer's disease”), (“education” or “schooling” or “literacy”), (“nutrition” or “stunting” or “body stature” or “short height”), (“women” or “gender”) and (“Africa” or “Nigeria” or “West Africa”).

Studies were included if they addressed dementia epidemiology, developmental determinants of health, metabolic risk factors, or sociopolitical influences on women's health in LMICs. The review integrates findings from epidemiology, developmental health science, sociology, and policy analysis to develop a conceptual framework linking structural determinants to dementia risk.

Social perspectives of Disease Epidemiology

From a sociopolitical perspective, these risk factors are not merely random biomedical occurrences; rather, they represent predictable outcomes of historical and

systemic disadvantage. Dementia in Nigerian women is more than a biological endpoint; it is a manifestation of entrenched sociocultural inequities, of varying types and dimensions. These inequities includes;

I, Limited access to childhood nutrition: This results in short stature, which is increasingly recognised as a proxy for early-life malnutrition and chronic childhood infections.¹⁰ Undernutrition during critical developmental periods compromises brain development and increases lifetime vulnerability to metabolic and neurodegenerative conditions.^{11,12} In Nigeria, female children are disproportionately affected by food insecurity in specific socio-environmental settings.¹³

II, Structural barriers to formal education: For the girl child, low education restricts cognitive reserve, limits health literacy, and reduces lifelong engagement in mentally stimulating activities.^{14,15} For the Nigerian women, especially those from rural or low-income households, access to formal education is reported to be restricted by gendered cultural norms and economic constraints, in many communities.¹⁶

III, Glucose dysfunction: chronic hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, and long-standing type 2 diabetes exerts direct neurotoxic effects, which accelerate brain aging and thus increase dementia risk.^{17,18} Some investigators have shown that Nigerian women often face delayed diagnosis and poor glycemic control due to limited access to metabolic screening and treatment.^{17,19,20,21}

IV, Gendered power imbalances: These imbalances limit health-seeking, autonomy and socioeconomic participation.¹⁶ This factor is further worsened by systemic poverty and political under-investment in women's long-term well-being,²² thus aiding above issues to increase dementia risk in them.

As illustrated in Table 1 below, the enumerated factors create a model of interaction in which social, biological, and political determinants exacerbate one another, thus disproportionately affecting the female population.^{23,24} Hence the belief in this work that public policy, whether through action or neglect, can shape exposure to risk factors from early childhood through adulthood.^{24,25}

While the biomedical associations are increasingly evident, the sociopolitical mechanisms underlying these risks remain underexplored.²⁶ This work, therefore, adopts a sociological and political economy approach to examine how Nigerian public policy can mitigate or exacerbate dementia risk in women.^{5,22}

Framing dementia prevention as both a biomedical and sociopolitical issue aligns with global calls for gender-responsive health policy and the World Health Organization's (WHO) emphasis on modifiable risk factors.^{1,2}

Table 1. Key Sociobiological Risk Factors for Dementia Among Nigerian Women

Risk Factor	Mechanism of Increased Dementia Risk	Policy-Relevant Indicator	Evidence Strength / Source
Low Educational Attainment	Lower cognitive reserve, reduced health literacy, poor disease self management	Female school completion rate; average years of schooling for women	Meta-analysis: each year of education reduces risk by ~7–8 %.
Short Adult Stature	Proxy for early -life undernutrition, infections → impaired neurodevelopment	Prevalence of stunting in female children; mean adult height	Cohort study: shorter adult height associated with higher dementia risk.
Glucose Dysfunction / Diabetes	Vascular damage, insulin resistance, inflammation	Female diabetes prevalence; glycemic control metrics	Meta-analysis: diabetes confers ~1.59-fold increased risk of dementia.

The above Table is synthesized from references 10, 16 and 17 .

Epidemiology of Dementia in Nigerian Women:

Dementia prevalence in Nigeria is agreed to be increasing, but the precise estimates remain unclear due to insufficient surveillance systems and diagnostic infrastructure.^{3,5} Community-based studies suggest rising incidence among adults aged 60 years and older, with higher prevalence observed among women.^{27,28} Several explanations have been proposed for this gender disparity. In addition to those mentioned above, women generally live longer than men, thus increasing exposure to age-related neurodegenerative diseases. However, structural determinants such as lower educational attainment, limited healthcare access, and socioeconomic disadvantage can play significant roles in present reality.^{6,16,29} Furthermore, Women in Nigeria frequently encounter barriers to early diagnosis and treatment of cognitive disorders, including limited health literacy, sociocultural stigma, and financial constraints.^{21,30} These factors contribute majorly to underdiagnoses in rural and peri-urban communities. At the same time, the rising prevalence of diabetes in Nigeria, affecting millions of adults, introduces an additional metabolic burden associated with accelerated cognitive decline.^{18,31-33}

Conceptual Framework; Social Determinants of Cognitive Aging:

The conceptual framework proposed in this review integrates three major theoretical perspectives: a, social determinants of health (SDH); b, developmental origins of health and diseases (DOHaD), and c, political economy of health.

The SDH framework emphasises that health outcomes are shaped by structural determinants such as education, income, gender inequality, and healthcare access.^{23,24,34} In Nigeria, these determinants intersect with cultural norms and regional disparities to influence women's health trajectories.^{16,22,23,35} Within this framework, structural determinants influence life-course exposures that affect biological pathways associated with dementia risk (See Figure 1 below). These pathways include impaired neurodevelopment resulting from childhood malnutrition, reduced cognitive reserve due to limited education, and metabolic dysfunction associated with diabetes. Over time, these interacting exposures create a syndemic pattern in which social and biological vulnerabilities reinforce each other, ultimately increasing dementia susceptibility.^{23,24}

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework of sociopolitical determinant and increased Dementia Risk

Developmental Origins of Health and Disease:

The Developmental Origins of Health and Disease (DOHaD) hypothesis provides critical insight into how early-life environments influence long-term health outcomes.^{36,37} Advances in epigenetics have demonstrated that environmental exposures during fetal development and early childhood can modify gene expression and metabolic programming.³⁸ These biological adaptations represent responses to anticipated environmental conditions. However, when early-life exposures differ substantially from later environments, individuals may experience increased susceptibility to chronic diseases such as diabetes and cognitive decline.^{11,12,13,39}

Short stature is widely recognized as a proxy for early-life nutritional deprivation, childhood infections, and socioeconomic stress,^{6,11,12,13} are modifiable health factors, when the right policies are put in place. These adverse exposures at critical life course junctures can impair neurodevelopment, reduce cognitive reserve, and increase susceptibility to metabolic diseases in adulthood.^{6,7,8,40} Consequently, short stature serves as both a biological marker and a sociopolitical indicator of childhood disadvantage as earlier reported in Nigeria^{6,7} Thus it underscore the critical relevance of these factors in developing national strategies to mitigate dementia.

Political Economy of Health:

The political economy of health framework highlights how governance structures, resource allocation and social power relations, shape health outcomes.^{22,25,26} Health disparities among Nigerian women are influenced not only by individual behaviors, but also by systemic factors including political priorities, institutional capacity, economic inequality, and gendered social structures.^{22,25,41} As illustrated in the conceptual framework in Figure 2 below, these multi-level determinants create a structural environment that dictates health outcomes, independently of clinical interventions. Furthermore, the absence of a national dementia strategy and limited investment in geriatric care reflect broader governance challenges affecting Nigeria's health system.^{5,42} This therefore indicate areas of added necessity for government and political intervention, in the overall desire to address dementia in the country, especially as it concerns women.

Figure 2: Political Economy of Dementia Risk in Nigerian women

Nigerian Women, Education, and Dementia Risk; Educational Inequality in Nigeria:

Education plays a central role in cognitive health by strengthening cognitive reserve, improving health literacy, and enhancing socioeconomic opportunities.^{14,15} Globally, higher educational attainment has been consistently associated with reduced risk of dementia. However, Nigeria continues to experience significant gender disparities in education, particularly in northern regions where poverty, early marriage, and sociocultural norms limit girls' access to schooling.^{40,43,44}

These disparities have long-term implications for women's health and wellbeing. Limited education reduces employment opportunities and restricts access to healthcare services, thereby increasing vulnerability to chronic diseases including metabolic diseases and dementia.^{6,40,45} Although initiatives such as the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program aim to improve access to schooling, implementation remains uneven due to funding limitations, insecurity, and governance challenges.⁴³ To support policy advocacy, empirical investigations have demonstrated that increased educational access for girls and women is associated with transformative, multi-generational changes within their respective communities.^{46,47,48} This can be in the form of gender specific initiatives for the girl child, in uniquely designed and supported education system. The suggestion is that such model will be development of schools that have meal support, provision of uniforms and other incentives to increase girl child school enrolment in basic education, especially in severely affected regions.⁴⁰

Short Stature as a Marker of Early-Life Structural Disadvantage:

Short stature among Nigerian women often reflects childhood malnutrition, repeated infections, and household food insecurity.⁴⁹ These factors are strongly influenced by structural determinants including agricultural policy, poverty, sanitation, and maternal healthcare systems. Research indicates that childhood stunting is associated with poorer cognitive

development, reduced educational attainment, and long-term health risks.¹² These disadvantages accumulate across the life course, increasing susceptibility to dementia. Persistent rates of childhood malnutrition in Nigeria suggest that current nutrition strategies remain fragmented and insufficiently implemented.^{13,34,50} Herein lies the import of the suggestion above for the institution of education policies and systems that preferentially encourages girl child in education attainment, without overtly relegating the need for the boys.⁴⁰

Diabetes, Metabolic Health, and Dementia:

The prevalence of type 2 diabetes is rising rapidly in Nigeria due to urbanization, lifestyle changes, and dietary transitions.^{31,32} Women face additional vulnerability due to biological and sociocultural factors affecting health behaviors and healthcare access. Diabetes contributes to dementia risk through multiple mechanisms including vascular damage, chronic inflammation, and insulin resistance.^{7,8,17,18,33} However, barriers to diabetes care remain widespread in Nigeria, including limited screening programs, inadequate healthcare infrastructure, and restricted decision-making autonomy among women.^{21,29,40}

Sociological Dimensions of Dementia Risk in Nigerian Women:

The sociological landscape of dementia in Nigeria is oiled by ingrained patriarchal norms and the pervasive impact of structural inequities in many communities. Associated gendered power dynamics systematically restrict women's access to fundamental determinants of health, including formal education, adequate nutrition, and timely healthcare.^{16,51} Within this framework, structural violence manifests not as an isolated event, but as a normalised, systemic deprivation that may create enduring physiological consequences.^{25,52} By framing these sociocultural inequities as a form of violence, it becomes evident that the high prevalence of dementia among Nigerian women is a predictable outcome of political and social structures that marginalise the female lifecycle.

Dementia risk in this population is best understood through a life-course perspective, where vulnerability

accumulates from the prenatal stage through old age.^{2,40} Each developmental milestone, characterized by poor maternal nutrition, low birthweight, childhood stunting, and restricted educational or employment opportunities, represents a cumulative sociopolitical failure that compromises cognitive reserve and increases metabolic risk.^{6,11,36,50} An intersectional analysis reveals that these vulnerabilities are not uniform; rather, they are layered by geographic region, socioeconomic class, and religious affiliation.⁴⁰ Consequently, women in northern rural communities often face the highest risk profile, as they exist at the nexus of multiple systemic disadvantages that compound to accelerate neurodegenerative decline.^{6,8,40}

Policy Context in Nigeria:

Nigeria's lack of a dedicated national dementia strategy

despite the growing burden of cognitive disorders,⁵ need to be addressed without further delay. Existing health policies primarily focus on infectious diseases and maternal health, while aging and dementia, and dementia social factors remain underprioritised. Several systemic challenges limit policy effectiveness, including fragmented governance structures, limited mental health funding, and weak implementation of national health and education programs.^{40,42} The specific policy gaps and their corresponding sociopolitical implications are summarized in Table 2 below. In particular, mental health spending in Nigeria remains disproportionately low relative to overall health expenditure, limiting the expansion of dementia services and the development of essential geriatric care infrastructure.⁵

Table 2. Policy Gaps in Nigeria Relating to Dementia Risk

Policy Domain	Current Status in Nigeria	Gap / Challenge	Potential Policy Leverage
Education	Universal Basic Education (UBE), but gender disparities persist	Low female retention, early marriage, poor school quality	Conditional cash transfers, girls' scholarships, enforcement of compulsory schooling
Nutrition/Early-Life Health	National nutrition plans, but fragmented	High rates of childhood stunting, low maternal nutrition coverage	Scaled-up maternal -child nutrition programs; integrated primary care nutrition services
Non-communicable Disease (NCD) / Diabetes	National NCD action plan; limited primary care capacity	Poor screening, low awareness, gendered access barriers	Community-based diabetes screening; women-friendly NCD clinics
Dementia / Aging Policy	No formal national dementia strategy	Lack of surveillance, no registries, weak care infrastructure	Develop a National Dementia Policy; invest in community health workers; integrate with primary care

Toward a Public Policy Agenda for Dementia Prevention in Nigerian Women:

Addressing dementia risk among Nigerian women requires comprehensive, life-course policy framework that spans multiple sectors and developmental stages. The conceptual architecture of this multi-stage approach is illustrated in Table 3 and Figure 3 which maps policy interventions from early childhood through late adulthood.

Within this framework, several key domains must be prioritized by Nigeria:

I. Educational Empowerment: Strengthening girls' education represents a critical strategy for improving long-term cognitive health outcomes. Policies that promote school retention, discourage early marriage,

and support adult literacy programs can enhance both cognitive reserve and socioeconomic opportunities.^{8,40,43,47}

II. Maternal and Early-Childhood Nutrition: Improving nutritional security is essential for mitigating neurodevelopmental risks. Expanded community-based nutrition programs and integrated maternal healthcare services are vital to addressing childhood stunting and its associated developmental disadvantages.^{11,13,40,50}

III. Metabolic Disease Management: Diabetes prevention and management programs should prioritize community-based screening, improved access to affordable treatment, and gender-responsive health education initiatives designed to reach women in underserved areas.^{31,32,40}

Nigeria would benefit significantly from establishing a comprehensive national dementia strategy. This should include robust surveillance systems, public awareness campaigns, and the integration of cognitive screening into primary healthcare services as has been advised in earlier studies.^{28,40,53,54}

Table 3. Proposed Life-Course Public Policy Interventions and Responsible Stakeholders

Life-Course Stage	Proposed Intervention	Responsible Sectors/ Actors	Success Indicators
Early Childhood	School feeding, micronutrient supplementation, infection control	Federal Ministry of Health; Ministry of Education; Local Governments	Reduction in child stunting rates; improved school attendance; micronutrient coverage
Adolescence / Young Womanhood	Incentivize girls' education, delay early marriage	Ministry of Women Affairs; Ministry of Education; NGOs	Girls' primary and secondary completion rates; age at first marriage
Midlife (Metabolic Health)	Diabetes screening, glycemic control, community NCD clinics	Ministry of Health, PHC centers, community health workers	Prevalence of uncontrolled diabetes; number of women screened; treatment coverage
Later Life (Aging)	Dementia awareness, screening, community dementia care	Ministry of Health; social services; local NGOs	Number of CHWs trained; dementia registry established; community -based support groups

Fig. 3: Life-course Intervention Model for management of community dementia prevalence (Diagram synthesised from information provided by Livingstone et al, 2020)

CONCLUSION

The rising burden of dementia among Nigerian women reflects a complex interaction of biological processes and structural determinants of health. Low educational attainment, early-life adversity, and metabolic disorders represent interconnected pathways shaped by social inequality and public policy environments.

Dementia prevention in Nigeria must therefore extend beyond clinical care to include investments in education, nutrition, healthcare access, and gender equity. A life-course approach that integrates

multisectoral policy action, offers the most effective pathway for reducing dementia risk and promoting healthy cognitive aging among Nigerian women.

Without sustained political commitment and coordinated reforms, Nigeria may face a substantial increase in preventable cognitive decline among aging populations. Conversely, strategic policy interventions have the potential to significantly improve long-term neurological health outcomes of Nigerians, especially women, with gender related policy development and management.

Declarations:

Ethics approval and consent to participate: Not applicable for this narrative review. This study is based on analysis of published literature and reports

Consent for publication: All authors have approved the final manuscript

Availability of data and materials: All data synthesized or analyzed during this study are included in this published article or cited sources

Competing interests: The authors declare that they have no competing interests

Funding: The authors received no specific funding for this work

Authors' contributions: EKO and EIB-A conceptualized the study. EKO and EIB-A conducted data extraction. EKO, EIB-A and MEG-G participated in drafting

Acknowledgments: The authors acknowledge all authorities whose publicly available data informed this review

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. Risk reduction of cognitive decline and dementia: WHO Guidelines Geneva: World Health Organization[Internet]. 2019 [cited 2026 Mar 23];13-45. Available from:<https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/312180/9789241550543-eng.pdf>
2. Livingston G, Huntley J, Sommerlad A, Ames D, Ballard C, Banerjee S, et al. Dementia prevention, intervention, and care: 2020 report of the Lancet Commission. *Lancet*. 2020; 396(10248): 413-446.
3. Prince M, Comas-Herrera A, Knapp M, Guerchet M, Karagiannidou M. World Alzheimer Report 2016: Improving healthcare for people living with dementia: coverage, quality and costs now and in the future. *Alzheimer's Disease International*[Internet]. 2016 [cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available from: <https://unilim.hal.science/hal-03495463/document>
4. Mbam KC, Halvorsen CJ, Okoye UO. Aging in Nigeria: A growing population of older adults requires the implementation of national aging policies. *The Gerontologist*. 2022; 62(9): 1243-1250.
5. Akinyemi RO, Yaria J, Ojagbemi A, Guerchet M, Okubadejo N, Njamnshi AK, et al. Dementia in Africa: current evidence, knowledge gaps, and future directions. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*. 2022; (4): 790-809.
6. Oghagbon EK, Giménez-Llort L. Short height and poor education increase the risk of dementia in Nigerian type 2 diabetic women. *Alzheimers Dement (Amst)*. 2019; 11: 493-499.
7. Giménez-Llort L, Oghagbon E, Dogo F, Ogiator M, Prieto-Pino J. Nigerian women are more susceptible to the impact of diabetes-and-dementia: State-of-art, Future perspectives and Directions. *Int Psychogeriatr*. 2020; 32(S1): 156.
8. Oghagbon EK, Prieto-Pino J, Dogoh F, Ogiator M, Giménez-Llort L. Diabetes/Dementia in Sub-Saharan Africa and Nigerian Women in the Eye of Storm. *Curr Alzheimer Res*. 2022; 19(2): 161-170.
9. Barbiellini Amidei C, Fayosse A, Dumurgier J, Machado-Fragua MD, Tabak AG, van Sloten T, et al. Association between age at diabetes onset and subsequent risk of dementia. *Jama*. 2021; 325(16): 1640-1649.
10. Jørgensen TS, Okholm GT, Christensen K, Sørensen TI, Osler M. Body height in young adult men and risk of dementia later in adult life. *Elife*. 2020; 9: e51168.
11. Victora CG, Adair L, Fall C, Hallal PC, Martorell R, Richter L, et al. Maternal and child undernutrition: consequences for adult health and human capital. *The lancet*. 2008; 371(9609): 340-357.
12. Grantham-McGregor S, Cheung YB, Cueto S, Glewwe P, Richter L, Strupp B. Developmental potential in the first 5 years for children in developing countries. *The lancet*. 2007; 369(9555): 60-70.

13. UNICEF Nigeria. Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey 2016–17: Key Findings[Internet]. Nigeria: UNICEF; 2017[cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available from:<https://ngfrepository.org.ng:8443/handle/123456789/3142>
14. Stern Y. Cognitive reserve in ageing and Alzheimer's disease. *Lancet Neurol.* 2012; 11(11): 1006-1012.
15. Meng X, D'Arcy C. Education and dementia in the context of the cognitive reserve hypothesis: a systematic review with meta-analyses and qualitative analyses. *PLoS One.* 2012; 7(6): e38268.
16. Adedini SA, Somefun OD, Odimegwu C. Gender inequality and maternal and child healthcare utilization in sub-Saharan Africa. *Gender and Behaviour.* 2014; 12(4): 6050-6070.
17. Xue M, Xu W, Ou YN, Cao XP, Tan MS, Tan L, et al. Diabetes mellitus and risks of cognitive impairment and dementia: A systematic review and meta-analysis of 144 prospective studies. *Ageing research reviews.* 2019; 55: 100944.
18. Biessels GJ, Despa F. Cognitive decline and dementia in diabetes mellitus: mechanisms and clinical implications. *Nat Rev Endocrinol.* 2018; 14(10): 591-604.
19. Sędzikowska A, Szablewski L. Insulin and insulin resistance in Alzheimer's disease. *International journal of molecular sciences.* 2021; 22(18): 9987.
20. Adedini SA, Odimegwu C, Bamiwuye O, Fadeyibi O, Wet ND. Barriers to accessing health care in Nigeria: implications for child survival. *Global health action.* 2014; 7(1): 23499.
21. Ugwu E, Onung S, Ezeani I, Olamoyegun M, Adeleye O, Uloko A. Barriers to diabetes care in a developing country: exploratory evidence from diabetes healthcare providers. *Journal of Advances in Medicine and Medical Research.* 2020; 32(10): 72-83.
22. Farmer P. Pathologies of power: Health, human rights, and the new war on the poor [Internet]. Univ of California Press; 2004. Available from: <https://www.ucpress.edu/book/9780520243262/pathologies-of-power>
23. Marmot M, Wilkinson R, editors. Social determinants of health [Internet]. Oup Oxford; 2005. Available from: https://digital.library.tu.ac.th/tu_dc/frontend/Info/item/dc:307024
24. World Health Organization. A conceptual framework for action on the social determinants of health, 2010.
25. Navarro V. The Political Economy of Social Inequalities: Consequences for Health and Quality of Life [Internet]. Routledge; 2002. Available from: <https://www.routledge.com/The-Political-Economy-of-Social-Inequalities-Consequences-for-Health-and-Quality-of-Life/Navarro/p/book/9780895032522>
26. Banks T, Dimond R. Nettleton, Sarah: The Sociology of Health and Illness 3rd. ed [Book Review]. *Medical Sociology Online.* 2013; 7(2): 78-79.
27. Ineichen B. The epidemiology of dementia in Africa: a review. *Social Science & Medicine.* 2000; 50(11): 1673-1677.
28. Ogunniyi A, Baiyewu O, Gureje O, Hall KS, Unverzagt F, Siu SH, et al. Epidemiology of dementia in Nigeria: results from the Indianapolis–Ibadan study. *European Journal of Neurology.* 2000; 7(5): 485-490.
29. Titus OB, Adebisola OA, Adeniji AO. Health-care access and utilization among rural households in Nigeria. *Journal of development and agricultural economics.* 2015; 7(5): 195-203.
30. Aboderin I. Intergenerational support and old age in Africa [Internet]. Routledge; 2017. Available from:<https://www.routledge.com/Intergenerational-Support-and-Old-Age-in-Africa/Aboderin/p/book/9781138511026>
31. Federation ID. IDF Diabetes Atlas 2021[Internet]. International Diabetes Federation. 2021. [cited

- 2026 Mar 23]. Available from: <https://www.medbox.org/document/idf-diabetes-atlas-2021>
32. Adeloye D, Ige JO, Aderemi AV, Adeleye N, Amoo EO, Auta A, Oni G. Estimating the prevalence, hospitalisation and mortality from type 2 diabetes mellitus in Nigeria: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ open*. 2017; 7(5): e015424.
 33. Chatterjee S, Peters SA, Woodward M, Mejia AS, Batty GD, Beckett N, et al. Type 2 diabetes as a risk factor for dementia in women compared with men: a pooled analysis of 2.3 million people comprising more than 100,000 cases of dementia. *Diabetes care*. 2016; 39(2): 300-307.
 34. World Health Organization. Global action plan on the public health response to dementia 2017–2025[Internet]. World Health Organization; 2017. [cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/global-action-plan-on-the-public-health-response-to-dementia-2017---2025>
 35. Krieger N. Embodiment: a conceptual glossary for epidemiology. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*. 2005; 59(5): 350-355.
 36. Gluckman PD, Hanson MA, Buklijas T. A conceptual framework for the developmental origins of health and disease. *Journal of Developmental Origins of Health and Disease*. 2010; 1(1): 6-18
 37. Langley-Evans SC, McMullen S. Developmental origins of adult disease. *Med Princ Pract*. 2010;19: 87-98,
 38. Lacagnina S. The Developmental Origins of Health and Disease (DOHaD). *Am J Lifestyle Med*. 2019; 14(1):47-50.
 39. Aiken CE, Ozanne SE. Transgeneration developmental programming. *Hum Reprod Update*. 2014; 20: 63-75
 40. Oghagbon EK, Ben-Ameh EI, Gimenez-Llort L. Life-course policies to address high dementia risk in Nigerian women should synergistically combat poor education and early-life nutrition disparities[Internet]. *BMC neurology*. 2026. [cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/41796288/>
 41. Farmer P. Pathologies of power: rethinking health and human rights. *Am J Public Health*. 1999; 89(10): 1486-1496.
 42. Federal Ministry of Health Nigeria. National Health Policy 2016[Internet]. Nigeria: FMOH: 2016 [cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available: <https://naca.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/National-Health-Policy-Final-copy.pdf>
 43. World Bank. Nigeria Education Sector Analysis[Internet]. World Bank: 2021 [cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available from: <https://education.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Education-Sector-Analysis-2021.pdf>
 44. United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF). Child marriage in West and Central Africa: A statistical overview and reflections on ending the practice[Internet]. New York: UNICEF: 2022 [cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available from: <https://data.unicef.org/resources/child-marriage-in-west-and-central-africa-a-statistical-overview-and-reflections-on-ending-the-practice/>
 45. Makai C, Familoye IT, Diekuu J-B. Breaking barriers: The impact of girls' education on poverty eradication in northern Nigeria – A Focus on Sokoto State. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*. 2024; 24(01): 1793–1797.
 46. Barcellos SH, Carvalho L, Langa KM, Nimmagadda S, Turley P. Education and dementia risk. *NBER Working Paper*. 2025;33430.
 47. Duflo E. Women Empowerment and Economic Development. *Journal of Economic Literature*. 2012; 50(4): 1051-1079.
 48. Zamarian L, Karner E, Bodner T, Djamshidian A, Delazer M. Differential impact of education on cognitive performance in neurological patients

- with progressive cognitive decline. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*. 2021;80(4):1491-501.
49. United Nations Children's Fund, World Health Organization, World Bank Group. Levels and Trends in Child Malnutrition: UNICEF / WHO / World Bank Group Joint Child Malnutrition Estimates[Internet]. Geneva: WHO: 2021 [cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available from : <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240112308>
 50. United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF). UNICEF Nigeria: Highlights 2018–2022 – Key results for children[Internet]. Abuja: UNICEF Nigeria: 2022 [cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available from : <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/media/7181/file/COAR.pdf>
 51. Federal Republic of Nigeria. National Gender Policy (2021–2026)[Internet]. Abuja: Federal Ministry of Women Affairs: 2021 [cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available from : <https://ngfrepository.org.ng:8443/jspui/handle/123456789/6582>
 52. Sen A. Freedom. Development[Internet] Oxford University Press, Oxford. 1999 [cited 2026 Mar 23]. Available from : https://raggeduniversity.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/1_x_senDevelopmentalFreedom-_compressed.pdf
 53. Dubbelman MA, Verrijp M, Facal D, Sánchez-Benavides G, Brown LJ, van der Flier WM, Jokinen H, Lee A, Leroi I, Lojo-Seoane C, Milošević V. The influence of diversity on the measurement of functional impairment: an international validation of the Amsterdam IADL Questionnaire in eight countries. *Alzheimer's & Dementia: Diagnosis, Assessment & Disease Monitoring*. 2020; 12(1): e12021.
 54. Angrist N, Jukes MC, Clarke S, Chico RM, Opondo C, Bundy D, Cohee LM. School-based malaria chemoprevention as a cost-effective approach to improve cognitive and educational outcomes: a meta-analysis. *NPJ Glob Public Health*. 2023; 3: 24.